

**INTERNATIONAL RESEARCH
AND PRACTICE CONFERENCE
“NANOTECHNOLOGY
AND NANOMATERIALS”**

**21-24 of August 2024
Uzhhorod, UKRAINE**

Abstract book

Anelasticity of SiO₂, multiwalled carbon nanotubes and polymers

Onanko A.P., Gaponov A.M., Onanko Y.A., Dmytrenko O.P., Kulish M.P., Pinchuk-Rugal T.M., Pavlenko O.L. Busko T.O., Kurochka L.I., Charnyi D.V., Yatsiuk M.V., Matselyuk E.M., Marysyk S.V., Ilyin P.P.

Kyiv national university, Volodymyrs'ka str., 64, Kyiv-01601, Ukraine.

E-mail: onanko@i.ua

Anelasticity of SiO₂, radiation and structural functionalized nanocomposites of multiwalled carbon nanotubes (MCNT) and polyamide-6 (NH(CH₂)₅CO)_n in Fig. 1, polyvinylchloride (C₂H₃Cl)_n, polyethylene (C₂H₄)_n were researched [1].

Fig. 1. Illustration of the window for processing data of quasitransversal elastic waves velocity measuring $V_{\perp} = 782$ m/sec in nanocomposite polyamide -6 + 0,1% MCNT by impulse phase ultrasonic method at frequency $f_{\perp} \approx 0,7$ MHz after electron irradiation with dose $D_e \approx 20$ Mrad with energy $E_e \approx 2.0$ Mev

Conclusions

1. The presence of the strong interaction for nanocomposites between polymers and multiwalled carbon nanotubes was confirmed by mechanical studies.

This work has been supported by the Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine: Grant of the Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine for the prospective development of the scientific direction "Mathematical sciences and natural sciences" at Taras Shevchenko National University of Kyiv.

Co-organizers of conference:

Institute of Physics of the NAS of Ukraine,
Ukraine;

Uzhhorod National University Ukraine;

University of Turin, Italy;

Pierre and Marie Curie University
and CNRS, France;

University of Tartu, Estonia;

Representative office of Polish
Academy of Sciences in Kiev;

EEN-Ukraine Consortium.

Interreg
Danube Region

Co-funded by
the European Union

EEN-Ukraine
consortium

RTIT>>

Partners of Conference

Springer

Taylor & Francis Group, LLC

Organizing Committee Members of conference:

Chairman: NASU academician A.G. Naumovets, Vice-President of the NAS of Ukraine;

Vice-Chairman: NASU academician L.P. Yatsenko, Director of Institute of Physics of the NAS of Ukraine;

NASU corresponding member A.V. Ragulia, Problems of Material Sciences Institute, NAS of Ukraine;

NASU corresponding member V.N. Uvarov, Metallophysics Institute, NAS of Ukraine;

NASU academician M.S. Brodyn, Institute of Physics, NAS of Ukraine;

NASU corresponding member A.M. Negriyko, Institute of Physics, NAS of Ukraine;

Petro Fochuk Yuriy Fedkovych Chernivtsi National University, Ukraine;

Yuriy Khalavka Yuriy Fedkovych Chernivtsi National University, Ukraine;

Victor Martynyuk, Taras Shevchenko national University of Kyiv;

Oleksandr Bediukh, Taras Shevchenko national University of Kyiv.

International Committee:

Prof. Henryk Sobczuk, Representative office „Polish Academy of Sciences” in Kyiv;

Dr. A. Damin, University of Turin, Italy;

Prof. Dr. habil. Emmanuelle Lacaze, Pierre and Marie Curie University and CNRS, France;

Prof. Bouchta Sahraoui, University of Angers, UFR Sciences, Institute of Sciences and Molecular Technologies of Angers, France;

Prof. Bakolas Dimitris, European Profiles A.E., Greece;

Dr. L.A. Dolgov, University of Tartu, Estonia;

Prof. Mohamed Bououdina, University of Bahrain, Kingdom of Bahrain;

Prof. Dr. Annemarie Pucci, Kirchhoff Institute of Physics of the Ruprecht-Karls University of Heidelberg, Germany.

This year, the conference is organized with the support of the

RTIT project, aimed at supporting small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in the materials sector. Over the next two years, the project will provide assistance to SMEs through a network of specialized communities in the Danube region, which plays a key role in materials production and manufacturing.

The Institute of Physics represents Ukraine as the executor of this project, working towards the creation and strengthening of knowledge communities and innovative methods in the field of materials science.

The RTIT project is implemented under the Danube Region Program and co-financed by the European Union, ensuring the necessary support and resources for the development of the materials sector.

Chairman of Local Committee and Secretary of Conference:

Dr. O.M. Fesenko, Institute of Physics of the NAS of Ukraine.

Local Committee:

Dr. A.D. Yaremkevych, Mr. Y.S. Kifiuk, Mr. M.V. Rallev, Dr. O.P. Budnyk, Dr. P.V. Golub, Mr. V.S. Tkachenko, Ms. A.V. Klochek, Ms. T.V. Tsebrienko, Dr. E.V. Leonenko, Mr. S. Starinets, Mr. V.O. Hryn.